

Effect of organic and inorganic nitrogen in acid sandy soil on upland rice yield

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In an experiment during the 1986 cropping season, poultry manure alone and in combination was compared with urea and calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN) in upland sandy loam and acidic soils of Amakama, Nigeria. The experimental design was a randomized complete block (RCB) with four replications.

Soil samples for analysis were taken after land preparation but before fertilizer application. Physical and chemical properties of the experimental soil are presented in Table 1. N was applied at 60 kg/ha. The poultry manure contained 0.66% N.

Poultry manure was incorporated 2 wk before planting, with 30 kg P and 40 kg K/ha applied basally. Urea and CAN were applied in 2 equal splits at 3 and 8 wk after planting. In the combinations, poultry manure at 30 kg N/ha was applied 2 wk before planting, and inorganic fertilizer at 30 kg N/ha was applied 8 wk after planting. Average monthly rainfall during crop growth was 218.8 mm.

The test crop was newly released upland rice FARO 41 (IRAT170). In the yield parameters considered, rice with poultry manure performed slightly, but not significantly, better than

Table 1. Physical and chemical analysis of experimental soil prior to planting, Amakama, Nigeria, 1986.

pH	4.6
Sand (%)	70.4
Silt (%)	10.4
Clay (%)	19.2
Organic matter (%)	1.025
N (%)	0.12
Available P (Bray I) (ppm)	50
K (meq/100 g)	0.40
Ca (meq/100 g)	0.66
Mg (meq/100 g)	0.96
Mn (ppm)	0.24
Zn (ppm)	5.8
Fe (ppm)	60.0

inorganic fertilizers (Table 2). The lack of significant difference could be attributed to considerable nutrient leaching on a sandy soil subjected to high rainfall for more than 6 mo of the year. Many and more vigorous weeds grew in poultry manure-treated plots. CAN depressed yield, even in

combination with poultry manure.

The results indicate that poultry manure can be used to supplement inorganic fertilizers. Poultry manure is cheap, easier to handle than other organic manure, and more available with an increase in the number of poultry farmers. □

Table 2. Response of yield parameters to N sources.^a Amakama, Nigeria, 1986.

N source	Tillers (no./m ²)	Productive tillers (no./m ²)	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Poultry manure	156	135	79	104	3.3
Urea	153	139	80	98	3.2
Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN)	134	118	81	94	2.8
Poultry manure + urea	138	117	79	101	3.2
Poultry manure + CAN	137	133	79	79	3.1
No N fertilizer	130	120	81	79	2.6
CV (%)	14	15	—		12.0
LSD	ns	ns			ns

^ans = not statistically significant.

Effect of floodwater depth on ammonia volatilization loss from urea in flooded soil

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Rate of ammonia volatilization in flooded rice soils can be estimated by monitoring floodwater parameters. But water depth may itself greatly influence the floodwater chemistry, and may influence rate of ammonia loss. We studied the effect of floodwater depth on ammonia volatilization, using a forced-draft chamber technique.

The soil was sandy loam (Typic Ustochrepts), pH 7.5, EC 0.15 dS/m, 0.32% organic C, 0.06% total N, and CEC 4.5 meq/100 g. Soil samples of 5 kg each were collected from the top 15 cm soil layer, air-dried, ground, and placed in 10-liter pots.

The soil was flooded, puddled, and allowed to preincubate with 1 cm standing water for 1 wk. It was then fertilized with 26 mg P and 50 mg K/kg, applied as single superphosphate and muriate of potash. Urea at 1.36 g N/pot (equivalent to 200 kg N/ha) was

broadcast and incorporated to 5–7 cm soil depth. The pots were reflooded to 25, 50, 100, and 125 mm depths. Evaporation losses were replenished daily.

Floodwater temperature ranged from 28 to 34 °C. Two pots of each treatment were covered with chambers continuously flushed with NH₃-free compressed air. NH₃ evolved from the incubated samples was collected at

1. Effect of floodwater depth on cumulative loss of ammonia from flooded sandy loam soil, Ludhiana, India.